

True Confession: Narratives of Persons Deprived of Liberty

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the lived experiences of incarcerated individuals, particularly focusing on the emotional, psychological, and social challenges they encounter during and after incarceration, as well as their coping mechanisms and perspectives on rehabilitation and reintegration. This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological research design. The study was conducted in a correctional facility in Davao City, Philippines, during the academic research period of 2025–2026. The study involved Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) who were selected through purposive sampling. In-depth interviews were conducted to gather detailed narratives regarding their experiences during incarceration. The interviews

focused on emotional struggles, mental health conditions, social relationships, coping strategies, and views on rehabilitation. Data were transcribed, coded, and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring themes and patterns related to the lived experiences of the participants. The findings revealed several dominant themes, including emotional distress due to separation from loved ones, mental health challenges such as anxiety and depression, and social stigma associated with incarceration. Participants reported the use of coping mechanisms such as spirituality, peer support, and self-reflection to manage psychological stress. Despite experiencing emotional and social difficulties, many PDLs expressed a strong desire for personal transformation and rehabilitation. The results further indicated that incarceration significantly affects emotional well-being but also provides opportunities for self-reflection and behavioral change. The study concludes that incarceration profoundly impacts the emotional, psychological, and social well-being of Persons Deprived of Liberty. However, it also highlights their potential for rehabilitation and personal growth. The findings underscore the need for enhanced mental health services, educational interventions, and reintegration programs within correctional facilities. Strengthening rehabilitative policies and reducing societal stigma can contribute to a more humane and effective criminal justice system that prioritizes rehabilitation over punishment.

Keywords: *Emotional Challenges, Incarceration, Person Deprived of Liberty, Rehabilitation, Stigma*

INTRODUCTION

Incarceration presents significant challenges that impact the overall well-being of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). While some individuals find opportunities for self-improvement through structured programs and personal reflection, many struggles with emotional distress, social isolation, and difficulties in reintegration. The lack of consistent support systems, combined with the stigma attached to imprisonment, makes it harder for former PDLs to rebuild their lives. Incarcerated individuals often

experience mental health issues, strained family relationships, and limited access to resources that could help them transition back into society. These challenges highlight the pressing need for effective rehabilitation programs, psychological support, and policies that promote successful reintegration rather than social exclusion. Thus, incarceration is not only a legal concern but also a pressing social and humanitarian issue.

Globally, Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) face numerous challenges that affects their physical, mental, and social well-being, with prison overcrowding being one of the most pressing concerns. Aon et al. (2025) revealed that overcrowding in prisons is strongly associated with negative health outcomes, including tuberculosis, COVID-19, self-harm, depression, overall prison mortality, and injuries due to violence. As the prison population increases, the prevalence of these health issues also rises, highlighting the urgent need for effective interventions. Also, the study *“Prison Overcrowding and Harsh Conditions: Health and Human Rights Concerns to Persons in Custody, Staff, and the Community”* exploring the overcrowding in Ghana prisons reported that the prison population of 15,228 far exceeds the official capacity of 10,265, resulting in poor living conditions, limited access to basic resources, psychological and emotional burdens, and heightened vulnerability to communicable diseases among persons in custody and prison officers (Baffour et al., 2022). These findings illustrate that overcrowding is not only a logistical and administrative challenge but also a critical human rights and public health issue. Understanding these trends, including the tangible consequences of exceeding prison capacity, is essential to contextualize and address the lived experiences of PDLs.

In the Philippine context, many PDLs encounter similar issues, including limited access to healthcare, overcrowding, inadequate mental health support, and persistent societal stigma. Local studies have revealed that even with available rehabilitation efforts, these are often underfunded, inconsistent, and insufficient in addressing the emotional and psychological needs of PDLs. The study by Ramirez (2023), *“Challenges Encountered by the Female Person Deprived of Liberty Amidst the Pandemic”*, highlighted the struggles of incarcerated women who faced poor access to hygiene products, health problems, and emotional isolation. Despite these hardships, many relied on diversion activities or faith to cope, reflecting both vulnerability and resilience. Furthermore, societal stigma remains one of the most significant challenges for people who have served their time in prison. Former PDLs often struggle to gain employment, reconnect with families, and reintegrate into their communities due to prejudices and misconceptions (Linaza et al., 2024). The lack of sustained support services worsens these challenges, making incarceration’s effects long-lasting even after release.

Specifically, in Davao City, rehabilitation initiatives exist but are far from sufficient. At the Davao City Jail Annex in Maa, congestion is rampant—cells designed for 300 inmates now house up to 900 due to pre-trial overcrowding PCIJ.org. Education programs like the College Education Behind Bars (CEBB) have helped some PDLs earn college degrees, with six recent graduates demonstrating the potential of these initiatives daily tribune. However, despite these achievements, many PDLs still express concerns about feeling isolated, unsupported, and unprepared for reintegration. Programs remain fragmented, and initiatives often lack sustained psychological and livelihood components that are grounded in PDLs’ lived experiences (Dejeto and Cabusao, 2022). While there are studies addressing conditions of incarceration, mental health interventions, and some reintegration programs, there remains a pronounced gap in research that gives central space to the firsthand narratives and lived experiences of PDLs—especially within the Davao Region. Existing programs like CEBB and mental health pilots show promise, but few studies elevate the personal voices of PDLs as the primary source of insight for reform. This study addresses this gap by providing a platform for PDLs to share their true confessions, cope mechanisms, and aspirations, thereby guiding the development of more humane and effective rehabilitation programs and informing broader societal understanding and destigmatization.

METHODS

Research Design

The present study adapts a phenomenological approach as the research design. According to Knaack (1984), phenomenology is the study of human experience from a particular perspective, and its purpose is to fully understand the structure and meaning of human experience. Furthermore, Braun and Clarke (2022) stated that thematic analysis is widely used in qualitative studies, as researchers can choose from a diverse range of approaches that can differ considerably in their conceptualizations of qualitative study, meaningful knowledge production, the criteria that construct the themes, and the analytic procedures. The aforementioned approach was selected due to its suitability to capture the subjective and deeply personal experiences of PDLs, wherein imprisonment may affect not only the participants but also their families, their mental health, and their perception of self-worth. Additionally, this approach will allow the participants to freely express their experiences, helping to bridge the gap between societal perceptions and the realities of being imprisoned (Saguran et al., 2023).

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the Davao City Jail Male Dormitory, located in the Davao Region, Philippines. The facility was selected primarily due to its proximity and accessibility to the researchers, which addressed practical constraints in terms of time, resources, and logistics. Conducting the study in a nearby correctional facility ensured feasibility, allowed for face-to-face interviews, and supported consistency in data gathering.

Figure 1. Map of the Philippines and Research Locale of the Study

Research Instrument

The study used a semi-structured interview guide to explore the lived experiences of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). It included open-ended questions on emotional challenges, coping strategies, and hopes for reintegration. The guide was flexible, allowing follow-up questions to explore participants' responses in more depth. This format enabled the researchers to maintain structure while still adapting to the flow of each conversation, ensuring that the narratives remained authentic and participant-centered.

Sampling Technique and Research Participants

This study utilized the purposive sampling technique, a non-probability sampling method that involved selecting participants based on predefined criteria aligned with the research objectives. The inclusion criteria required that participants (1) must be Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) who have been incarcerated for at least one year, (2) are able to express themselves clearly during interviews, and (3) voluntarily agreed to participate in the study. Individuals with mental conditions that hinder communication

or who chose not to participate were excluded. This approach ensured that only individuals who could provide relevant and important contributions to the understanding of the phenomenon being examined were included. The research focused on eight Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) to facilitate a comprehensive and in-depth examination of their lived experiences. The eight (8) participants included five (5) men, one (1) senior citizen, and two (2) members of the LGBTQ community, each representing different backgrounds and situations within incarceration.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection process adopted a structured yet flexible approach to ensure the gathering of detailed and pertinent information, while adhering to ethical standards. According to Adeoye-Olatunde and Olenik (2021), semi-structured interviews stand out because they balance the structure of guided questions with the freedom for participants to express their views in depth. The main tool used to gather data was a semi-structured interview guide for In-Depth Interviews (IDI), with open-ended questions based on the research objectives. Follow-up questions were asked to get deeper answers and richer stories. The researchers sought and obtained a letter of consent to conduct this research from Davao Central College. They then secured formal approval from correctional facility authorities and ethics committees and coordinated with jail administrators to schedule interviews. The identification of eligible participants was guided by inclusion criteria. The researchers explained the study's objectives, confidentiality measures, and voluntary participation policy, and obtained informed consent before conducting interviews. This step ensured that ethical considerations such as respect for autonomy, privacy, and dignity were upheld throughout the research process. During the interview process, the researchers used field notes to document the participants' responses, manually writing their answers on paper due to restrictions on audio or video recording devices inside the correctional facility. The researchers transcribed and analyzed the interview responses to ensure accuracy and conducted member-checking, where participants reviewed their transcribed responses for verification and validation. This strengthened the trustworthiness of the data and upheld the participants' ownership of their narratives.

Data Analysis Tool

Thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step framework, was used to analyze the data. Kiger and Varpio (2020) noted that thematic analysis is one of the most flexible methods for identifying and describing qualitative data. It emphasizes how versatile it is in handling complex data sets and its usefulness in various research contexts. This approach allowed the researchers to gain an in-depth understanding of the participants' lived experiences and provided a structured method for interpreting the data. It also helped ensure that emerging patterns were grounded in the voices and realities of the participants themselves. The researchers read and re-read the transcriptions to identify patterns and key ideas. Significant statements and experiences were labeled with codes, which were then grouped into broader themes based on recurring patterns. The themes were refined by comparing them with the full data set, and each theme was clearly described, explaining its relevance to the study's objectives. To strengthen the trustworthiness of the findings, the researchers ensured consistency in theme interpretation and alignment with research questions. Organized findings were compiled into comprehensive reports that directly incorporated the participants' quotes to support the key themes. This ensured that the analysis remained faithful to the voices of the PDLs, preserving the authenticity of their lived experiences.

Ethical Considerations

In adherence to ethical considerations, the researchers ensured that consent was obtained from all participants prior to conducting the interviews. This process involved clearly explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and participants' rights, including their right to withdraw at any time without consequences. Additionally, the researchers maintained strict confidentiality by anonymizing the data and storing all physical documents in a secured location to prevent unauthorized access. Participants were assigned pseudonyms or codes to protect their identities. No digital recordings or files were used; all

information was handled manually to safeguard privacy and ensure secure handling of sensitive data. The researchers also created a respectful, non-coercive environment during data collection to protect the participants' well-being and privacy. The researchers made an extra effort to ensure that the participants felt emotionally and psychologically safe during the interviews. Ethical approval was obtained from relevant institutional authorities, reinforcing the study's commitment to upholding the dignity and rights of Persons Deprived of Liberty.

RESULTS

This section discusses the results of the in-depth interviews from the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), using the Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis framework. The findings are categorized into themes based on the objectives of the study and are outlined in tables. Emergent themes, central ideas, and significant responses are displayed in each table, as well as a descriptive interpretation of their meaning from the participants' perspectives. To maintain clarity and confidentiality, each participant is assigned a label according to their profile: IDI-PM for Male PDLs, IDI-PS for Senior PDLs, and IDI-PL for LGBTQ+ PDLs. These identifiers are consistently used across the presentation of data.

Table 1: *The experiences of PDL in relation to their well-being*

This table presents the emotional and psychological experiences of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) during incarceration. Participants expressed deep emotional struggles brought on by separation from family, the sudden loss of personal freedom, and the intense mental burden of adjusting to prison life. Many described sleepless nights, emotional breakdowns, and feelings of helplessness. Coping mechanisms such as faith, prayer, and self-discipline gradually emerged as they adjusted to the harsh reality of confinement.

Emergent Themes	Core Ideas	Significant Responses
Loss and Longing	Separation from family causing intense longing	<p>IDI-PM3 (RO1; MQ1): "Lisod kaayo labaw na mingawon ko sakong pamilya... usahay muhangad nalang ko sa langit mag tanga maghunahuna nila pero okay naman. Naanad nako ani na situation, pero inig magabie gyud diha gyud mutukar akong gibati basta maghigda nako." <i>("It is very difficult especially when I miss my family... sometimes I just look up at the sky and think about them, but it's okay. I have gotten used to this situation, but at night, that's when my feelings really come back while I'm lying down.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PL6 (RO1; MQ1): "Unang problema or issue nako kay layo akung pamilya walay mo comfort nako..." <i>("My first problem or issue here is being far from my family, with no one to comfort me...")</i></p>
	Difficulty accepting imprisonment and loss of freedom	<p>IDI-PS4 (RO1; MQ1): "Issue about sakong sarili nga di nako madawat akong pagkapiso. Lisod kaayo dawaton. Mao nagaduol gyud ko sa Ginoo aron madawat na nako akong kahimtang." <i>("The issue I have with myself is that I cannot accept being imprisoned. It is really hard to accept. That is why I always draw closer to God so that I can accept my situation.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PM8 (RO1; MQ1): "So far pag abot nako diria dili lalim ang pag pamoyo maniid lang jud ka dili nimo dapt pugson ang dili nimo kaya buhaton" <i>("So far, when I arrived here, life was not easy. You just observe others, and you should not force yourself to do something that you cannot handle.")</i></p>
	Emotional and Mental Struggles	<p>IDI-PM2 (RO1; MQ1): "Issues daghan jud diri, and grabe kalisod gyud. Sugod palang inig sulod nimo diri gamay jud kaayo ang selda, mao akong una nakita gyud. Lisod katong bago palang ko pero naanad raman ko. Sa pagkaon wala may problema kay makakaon man ko sa saktong oras. Ang kalisod gyud kay nawalaan ko ug liberty, personal space, mga pagkaon nga lami, and nausab pud akong pakikitungo sa kapwa labaw na daghan kaayo mi diri PDL." <i>("There are so many issues here, and it's really hard. From the moment you enter, the cell is very small, that's the first thing I noticed. It was really difficult at first, but eventually, I got used to it. With food, I have no problem because I can eat at the right time. The real hardship is losing my liberty, personal space, the delicious foods I used to enjoy, and also my way of relating to others has changed, especially because there are so many of us PDLs here.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PM2 (RO1; PQ1.1): "Ang pag co-exist sa kapwa PDL. Lahi jud siya sa daghan nga aspect and diri ra nako naexperience ang mga butang like hierarchy and naay limits gyud sa pakikisama. Wala nako naisip nga sa isa ka selda naay privilege gyud ang matag usa saamoa. Dako kaayo nag apekto sa akoang mental state kay lisod kaayo diri miski pagtulog. Igo kaayo akoang mental state gyud, dako kaayog epekto. Naa na tanan diri anxiety and depression. Isa sa nakatabang sako kay ang pag apil sa mga programs diri sa sulod, mao ra akong pamaagi para malingaw ko." <i>("Co-existing with fellow PDLs is very different in many aspects, and I only experienced things like hierarchy and limits in social</i></p>

		<p><i>interaction here. I never thought that in one cell, each of us would have different privileges. It greatly affects my mental state because life here is really difficult, even in sleeping. My mental state is badly affected, with everything here—anxiety and depression. One thing that helps me is joining the programs inside, that’s the only way I can entertain myself.”)</i></p>
Prison Culture and Environment	Adjustment Through Observation and Caution	<p>IDI-PM7 (RO1; PQ1.2): “Permi pundo-paniid ko diri. Dili ko mag pataka na kabalo ko ani tas pagkahuman dili diay mamao ang trabaho.” <i>(“I always stay quiet and observant here. I don’t act as if I know how to do something, only to find out later that I’m wrong.”)</i></p> <p>IDI-PL6 (RO1; PQ1.2): “Ginalingaw lang gyud nako akong sarili diri sama sa pag apil sa ilang mga programa. Mao gyud na isa sa rason ngano dili kaayo ko mabuang diri sa sulod. Always lang nako gina-apply ang awareness pud sa palibot and saakong sarili.” <i>(“I really just find ways to entertain myself here like joining their programs. That is really one of the reasons why I don’t go crazy inside. I always apply awareness of my surroundings and to myself.”)</i></p>
	Acceptance of internal structures and new roles	<p>IDI-PM7 (RO1; MQ1): “Diria sa sulod ang amoang naandan sa gawas dili gyud pareha kay sa gawas mabuhat nimo ang tanan naa kay freedom to choose pero diria sa sulod naa nay laing pamalaod ug mga buhaton naa mi mga kanya kanya diri ang grupong nga mao na ang nag patuman sa balaod diria sa sulod para sa pakig hiusa sa mga naa sa sulod murag brotherhood ba diria sa sulod limit ra o di numero ang imong lihok kay in every action na dili maayu naa jud consequences mao nang han ay kami na naa sa sulod...” <i>(“Inside here, what we are used to outside is not the same. Outside you can do everything and you have freedom to choose, but here inside there are rules and things to follow. We have our own groups that enforce the rules here inside for unity, kind of like brotherhood. Your actions are limited, because for every bad action there are consequences. That’s why we are organized here inside.”)</i></p> <p>IDI-PM3 (RO1; PQ1.1): “Magbilang diri. Naay bilang diri, sacred kaayo na saamoang kay kung makulangan mi meaning ana naay nitakas or nitago. Maong kailangan gyud basta bilang na kay present gyud tanan. Kung wala ka sa bilang kay kabalo nagyud ka unsay dangatan nimo kay maperwisyo man gud ang uban kaubanan sa sulod. Mao gyud nay nakalahi diri sa sulod ug sa gawas.” <i>(“We do roll calls here. Roll call is very sacred to us because if someone is missing, it means someone escaped or is hiding. That’s why it is really necessary that everyone is present during roll call. If you are absent, you already know what will happen because your companions will be affected. That’s what makes the life inside different from the outside.”)</i></p>

Inner Transformation	Constructive Routines	<p>IDI-PL5 (RO1; PQ1.2): “Naga apil ko sa mga activities dre sa sulod like Zumba akoy naga tudlo ug sayaw and human sulod nami sa among selda pagka hapon. Routine nko before matulog naga meditate ko Early ko nagamata 4:30 human 6 to 7 mag asikaso sa breakfast. Sleeping time nako Wala pero pag ma bored ko matulog nko.”</p> <p><i> (“I join activities here inside like Zumba, I’m the one teaching dance, and then afterwards we return to our cells in the afternoon. My routine before sleeping is meditation. I wake up early at 4:30 and from 6 to 7 I prepare breakfast. I don’t have a fixed sleeping time, but when I get bored, that’s when I sleep.”)</i></p> <p>IDI-PM2 (RO1; PQ1.2): “Nagabalik-balik sakoang hunahuna nga naa ko sa prisohan. Gina hunahuna nako nga dili nani mao ang situation nga mabuhat pa nako akong gusto, sanayan lang gyud ba. Gina hunahuna nako nga giisolate ko para sa kaayuhan sa mga tao. Everyday gyud nako na ginaatubang sakong sarili. Mao nagajoin ko sa program and activities diri sa sulod para matabangan nako akoang sarili. Kada adlaw nalang man pud gud nga nagasulod ang kaguol sakoang hunahuna ug dughan pero dili gyud baya lalim nga mag endure ani nga situation...”</p> <p><i> (“It keeps repeating in my mind that I’m in prison. I keep thinking that this is no longer the kind of situation where I can do whatever I want—just need to get used to it. I think of it as being isolated for the good of the people. Every day I face myself. That’s why I join programs and activities here inside to help myself. Almost every day, sadness enters my mind and chest, but it is really not easy to endure this situation.”)</i></p>
	Spiritual Growth and Acceptance	<p>IDI-PS4 (RO1; MQ1): “Lisod kaayo dawaton. Mao nagaduol gyud ko sa Ginoo aron madawat na nako akong kahimtang. Ang CR diri lisod kaayo. Pero pagkaabot ug 1 year to 2 years nako diri sa sulod medyo na-okay na, naanad nako.”</p> <p><i> (“It is very hard to accept. That is why I always draw closer to God so that I can accept my situation. The comfort rooms here are very difficult to use. But after one to two years of being here inside, I slowly became okay, I got used to it.”)</i></p> <p>IDI-PS4 (RO1; PQ1.2): “Always pray and salig lang sa Ginoo. Dili gyud ka magpadala sa init sa ulo, magpakumbaba gyud ta permi. Basta naa kay pasensiya, naa gyud kay kabutangan nga maayo.”</p> <p><i> (“Always pray and just trust God. Do not let anger control you, always remain humble. As long as you have patience, you will surely end up in a good place.”)</i></p>

The early stages of imprisonment proved to be emotionally overwhelming for most participants. They often endured long nights of homesickness and emotional isolation, even when surrounded by others. The inability to connect with family members and the psychological impact of confinement left lasting effects on their emotional well-being.

Table 2: *The effects of incarceration on the overall well-being of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)*

This table outlines the psychological, emotional, and behavioral effects of incarceration on the overall well-being of PDLs. The participants highlighted the mental toll of restricted autonomy, lifestyle changes, and the inability to interact with loved ones. While many struggled with depression and anxiety, some also experienced internal growth through reflection, spiritual development, and increased discipline. The data reflects a complex mix of emotional vulnerability and strength shaped by the prison environment.

Emergent Themes	Core Ideas	Significant Responses
Psychological and Emotional Impact of Incarceration	Loss of Freedom Triggers Psychological Strain	<p>IDI-PM1 (RO2; MQ2): "Naapektuhan gyud kog dako kay lahi ang ginabuhay nako sa gawas kesa diri sa sulod. Sa gawas makabuhay ka sa imong gusto nga buhaton, diri sa sulod dili nimo mabuhay imong gusto. Gipugos nako ug adjust kay para dili ko magka-anxiety og ma-depress." <i>("I was really affected because the things I used to do outside are very different from what I do here inside. Outside, you can do whatever you want, but here inside you cannot. I forced myself to adjust so that I would not develop anxiety or depression.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PM6 (RO2; MQ2): "Dako kaayog epekto kay sa gawas tanan gusto nako buhaton mabuhay man nako tanan gusto nako kaonon makaon man nako pero diri tanan butang naay limitations." <i>("It has a big effect because outside I could do everything I wanted, eat anything I wanted, but here everything has limitations.")</i></p>
	Onset of Depression and Anxiety	<p>IDI-PM7 (RO2; MQ2): "Normal lang depression anxiety labi na nga dapat ako unta ang naa didtoa." <i>("Depression and anxiety are normal, especially because I feel that I should not even be here.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PM8 (RO2; MQ2): "Kamingaw sa pamilya mag sunot ba negative na problema labi na sakit ang isa ka pamilya." <i>("The longing for family adds to the problems, especially when a family member is sick.")</i></p>
	Awareness of Personal Consequences	<p>IDI-PM3 (RO2; MQ2): "Respeto sa mga kaubanan. Kana gyud nausab gyud akong respeto sa mga tao tungod nila. Nirespeto man sad sila nako kay tungod sakong naabot sakong kinabuhi sama anang taas kog nahuman sa pagskwela. Respetohay gyud mi diri and kabalo nako makisama ug tao." <i>("My respect for others has changed. It really grew because of them. They also respected me because of my achievements in life, like finishing my studies. Here we respect one another, and I have learned how to relate to people.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PS4 (RO2; MQ2): "Dako kaayo. Ngano na-loob ko nga dili man dapat. Gidawat ko nalang. Mao mani ginatawag na consequences. Mas gidisiplina na nako akong sarili karon." <i>("It has a big effect. At first, I felt bitter about being here when I shouldn't have been. I just accepted it. This is what they call consequences. Now, I have become more disciplined with myself.")</i></p>

Changes in Behavior and Perspective	Spiritual Transformation and Reflection	<p><i>really regret it. I never expected to end up here because of what happened. Now, I go to church. I also teach here inside. There are really big changes in myself because I became a teacher here, and I am able to help my fellow inmates.”)</i></p> <p>IDI-PM2 (RO2; PQ2.1): "Mas naging sensitive pako sakong sarili, sa kauban nako, kato, compassionate ko karon ug mas controlado na nako akong emotion." (<i>"I became more sensitive to myself and my fellow inmates. I became more compassionate now, and I can control my emotions better."</i>)</p>
	Regret and Learning from the Past	<p>IDI-PM3 (RO2; PQ2.1): "Narealize nako na wala gyud nay ayo ang bisyo. Kanang mga barkada wala gyud nay ayo. Mahay kaayo sakong gibuhay tungod sa impluwensiya sa mga amigo nga dili maayo. Maong mas maayo gyud kung mamili mog tarong nga kauban sa gawas samtang naa moy freedom." (<i>"I realized that vices are really useless. Those kinds of friends are worthless. I regret what I did because of the influence of bad peers. That's why it's really better to choose good company while you still have freedom outside."</i>)</p> <p>IDI-PS4 (RO2; PQ2.1): "Makahunahuna nako nga magbago nagyud ko labaw kay lisod kaayo diri labaw na sa kaon, daghan kaayo ug bawal. Pag sa gawas pa ko makakaon kog mga lami and mabuhay nako akong mga gusto maski unsa pang orasa." (<i>"I realized that I really need to change, especially since life here is very hard, especially the food, and there are so many restrictions. When I was outside, I could eat good food and do whatever I wanted at any time."</i>)</p>
	Adopting Disciplined Behavior	<p>IDI-PL5 (RO2; PQ2.1): "Kanang problemado kaayo ka wala kay ma istoryahan kay maulaw ka mo share ug problems and Kaning kung unsaon pod nimo pag halobilo sa tao nga dili nimo kaila, kung unsa ilang Batasan so always be careful lang jud tas kailangan makisama sa environment dre sa sulod." (<i>"It's really hard when you have problems but no one to talk to because you are ashamed to share them. Also, you have to learn how to socialize with people you don't know and understand their attitudes. So you really need to be careful and learn how to adapt to the environment here inside."</i>)</p> <p>IDI-PL6 (RO2; PQ2.1): "Naa kay sa katong wala pako na priso walay makabuot kung unsay gusto nakong buhaton pero diri sa kulungan kung unsay gusto nila akong tumanon kay kung dili ko motuman naa may consequence." (<i>"Before I was imprisoned, no one controlled what I wanted to do. But here in prison, I have to follow what they want, because if I don't, there will be consequences."</i>)</p>
Coping and Emotional Regulation Strategies	Spiritual Resilience and Family as Strength	<p>IDI-PM1 (RO2; PQ2.2): "Magbasa-basa nalang ko. Dako jud ko ug kamingaw sa akong pamilya. Ginastorya-storya nalang nako sa akong mga kauban nga piniriso, gatudlo nalang ko nila magbasa saila, magbasa ug history and bible. Mga libro nga naa diri." (<i>"I just read books. I really miss my family. I just talk to my fellow inmates, and I also teach them to read. I read history books and the Bible. Just the books available here."</i>)</p> <p>IDI-PL6 (RO2; PQ2.2): "Akong pinaka una ge buhat kay ampo sampit jud sa Ginoo kay wala may lain makatabang sa ako kundi si God lang syempre consider na ang family sila naga motivate sa ako aron mabuhi pa." (<i>"The very first thing I did was pray and call on God, because no one else can really help me but Him. Of course, my family also motivates me to keep on living."</i>)</p>

	Seeking Social Connection for Support	<p>IDI-PM3 (RO2; PQ2.2): "Ginahunahuna lang gyud nako akong mga anak ug makighalubilo lang ko sa mga kaubanan nako dirisa sulod and sabayan pud nakog pag-ampo." <i>("I just think about my children, and I socialize with my fellow inmates here inside, accompanied by prayer.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PS4 (RO2; PQ2.2): "Always pray lang gyud. Unya mu-jam lang kog storya nga tarong sa mga kaubanan nako sa sulod. Makighalubilo sa sakto ba pampawala sa buryong diria sa sulod." <i>("I always just pray. Then I spend time chatting properly with my fellow inmates here inside. Socializing in the right way helps remove boredom inside.")</i></p>
	Productive Activities to Alleviate Emotional Stress	<p>IDI-PM2 (RO2; PQ2.2): "Naga observe ko kong onsay nahitabu sa sulod gina emphatise nako akong sarili. Daghan man gud nahitabo diri. Ginabutang nako more on observation and apply lang ko. Sensitive kaayo ang mga tao diri. Higitan gyud dapat ang awareness para mapreserve ang kahapsay ug kalinaw." <i>("I observe what is happening inside and empathize with myself. A lot really happens here. I focus more on observation and apply what I learn. People here are very sensitive. Awareness is really important to maintain order and peace.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PL5 (RO2; PQ2.2): "Makig istorya sa comfortable people nga pwede nimo sultian sa imong problems ug mag apil sa activities ug mag basa ug books and always pray." <i>("I talk to people I am comfortable with, people I can share my problems with. I also join activities, read books, and always pray.")</i></p>

Participants described their confinement as both damaging and eye-opening. The absence of freedom and loss of control over their routines led to emotional strain, especially in solitude. Despite the mental weight of imprisonment, several participants showed signs of personal transformation, driven by self-reflection and the desire to change for their families and future.

Table 3: *Insights shared by Persons Deprived of Liberty in managing self to achieve overall well-being*

This table captures the various self-management strategies used by PDLs to maintain their well-being while incarcerated. Responses reveal that faith, prayer, and a strong connection to family serve as emotional anchors. Involvement in programs, volunteer work, and new responsibilities also help them regain a sense of purpose. Despite limitations, many PDLs rely on inner strength, motivation, and spiritual grounding to stay resilient and hopeful about their future.

Emergent Themes	Core Ideas	Significant Responses
Spiritual Resilience as Foundation of Strength	Faith and Prayer as Pillars of Strength	<p>IDI-PM1 (RO3; MQ3): "Ampo gyud sa Ginoo, mao gyud nay solusyon kay siya na nakabalo sa tanan butang sa kalibutan." <i>("Pray to God, that is really the solution because He is the one who knows everything in this world.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PS4 (RO3; MQ3): "Pray lang gyud and tiwala lang sa Ginoo, gatawag pud ko sako pamilya gakumusta. Madungog lang nako sila, okay nako ana." <i>("I just pray and put my trust in God. I also call my family to ask how they are. Just hearing their voices is already enough for me.")</i></p>
		<p>IDI-PM2 (RO3; MQ3): "Ang akong selda doul sa chapel mas gaan akong loob kay nagasamba ko permi. Naa nay peace akong mind and na regain nako akong connection sa Ginoo." <i>("My cell is near the chapel, so I feel lighter because I can always worship. My mind has peace and I regained my connection with God.")</i></p>

	Connection to Divine Brings Peace of Mind	<p>IDI-PM3 (RO3; MQ3): "Always pray and be positive. Pray spiritually. Mao gyud nay sandigan nako permi ug maningkamot para sakong sarili kay wala man lain mutabang nako kundi akong sarili raman gyud." <i>("Always pray and be positive. Pray spiritually. That is always my foundation and I strive for myself because no one else can help me but myself.")</i></p>
	Strength Through Acceptance and Reflection	<p>IDI-PL6 (RO3; MQ3): "Pag abot nako diri nag apply ko sa I.N.S (Inmate Not Sentenced og V.A (Violation of Anti-Drug Law) para dili ko ma bored aron naa pud koy mabuhat kay kung walakoy buhaton ma depress man jud ko padulong og tungod pud sa pag apil nako anang ilang mga program nahimo kong president sa DOLE." <i>("When I arrived here, I applied for I.N.S (Inmate Not Sentenced) and V.A (Violation of Anti-Drug Law) so that I wouldn't get bored and so I would have something to do. If I have nothing to do, I might become depressed. Because of joining their programs, I became president of DOLE.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PM7 (RO3; MQ3): "Para sako gusto nako pag gawas nako lahi ko nga tao pra sakoang pamilya." <i>("For me, when I get out, I want to be a different person for my family.")</i></p>
Motivation Rooted in Family and Redemption	Loved Ones as Source of Strength	<p>IDI-PM8 (RO3; MQ3): "First of all akoo motivation nako akoang pamilya." <i>("First of all, my motivation is my family.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PS4 (RO3; MQ3): "Pray lang gyud and tiwala lang sa Ginoo, gatawag pud ko sako pamilya gakumusta. Madungog lang nako sila, okay nako ana." <i>("I just pray and put my trust in God. I also call my family to ask how they are. Just hearing their voices is already enough for me.")</i></p>
	Desire to Become a Better Person for Family	<p>IDI-PL5 (RO3; MQ3): "I think nga Ma feel nakoo nga naa Koy pulos Dre Kay sa gawas Kay Sige ralog laag. Maka function pako dire like mag assist dre kesa ditto sa gawas murag naa Koy purpose maka contribute pako dre. Wala hero ug wlay villain "sa panan aw sa ubang tao evil ka sa ila". If maka sala naka murag gina judges na dayun ka." <i>("I think I feel that I have a purpose here, unlike outside where I would just wander around. Here, I can still function, like assisting inside, and it feels like I have a purpose and I can contribute. There are no heroes or villains—'in the eyes of others, you are evil.' If you commit a mistake, people will immediately judge you.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PM3 (RO3; MQ3): "Always pray and be positive. Pray spiritually. Mao gyud nay sandigan nako permi ug maningkamot para sakong sarili kay wala man lain mutabang nako kundi akong sarili raman gyud." <i>("Always pray and be positive. Pray spiritually. That is always my foundation and I strive for myself because no one else can help me but myself.")</i></p>
	Realization of Purpose Despite Incarceration	<p>IDI-PL6 (RO3; MQ3): "Pag abot nako diri nag apply ko sa I.N.S (Inmate Not Sentenced og V.A (Violation of Anti-Drug Law) para dili ko ma bored aron naa pud koy mabuhat kay kung walakoy buhaton ma depress man jud ko padulong og tungod pud sa pag apil nako anang ilang mga program nahimo kong president sa DOLE." <i>("When I arrived here, I applied for I.N.S (Inmate Not Sentenced) and V.A (Violation of Anti-Drug Law) so that I wouldn't get bored and so I would have something to do. If I have nothing to do, I might become depressed. Because of joining their programs, I became president of DOLE.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PM2 (RO3; MQ3): "Ang akong selda doul sa chapel mas gaan akong loob kay nagasamba ko permi. Naa nay peace akong mind and na regain nako akong connection sa Ginoo."</p>

		<i>("My cell is near the chapel, so I feel lighter because I can always worship. My mind has peace and I regained my connection with God.")</i>
Wisdom Gained Through Hardship	Advice from Experience	<p>IDI-PM1 (RO3; PQ3.1): "Dapat dili magbuhat ug dautan na ika-silot nila. Focus sa pamilya, hatagan ug gahin ang pamilya nga importansiya kay sila rajud mo tabang inig walay barkada." <i>("One must not do evil that would bring punishment. Focus on the family, give them importance, because they are the only ones who will help you when friends are gone.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PM3 (RO3; PQ3.1): "Palayo gyud sa bisyo. Ayaw nalang gyud mog testing miski pa muingon mog kaisa ra, ayaw gyud kay naa sa ulahi ang pagmahay. Tong naa ko sa seminary dati didto man to nagsugod akoo, nitry rapud ko pero naanad naman nuon ko maong gamahay gyud kog taman. Iwas nalang gyud mo." <i>("Stay away from vices. Don't even try them, even if you say it's just once, don't do it because regret always comes last. Back when I was in the seminary, that's where it started. I just tried it once but I got used to it, and now I regret it so much. So really, avoid it.")</i></p>
	Faith and Positivity in Times of Darkness	<p>IDI-PL5 (RO3; PQ3.1): "Do a good term daily ug always believe in god problema na Gani Siya huna2 on pa nimo samot kag ka problema. And higugmaon nimo imong sarili ug be positive bisag ani ang situation nga problema." <i>("Do a good deed daily and always believe in God. If you already have a problem, and you keep thinking about it, the problem will only grow bigger. Love yourself and be positive even if the situation is difficult.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PS4 (RO3; PQ3.1): "Importante tiwala lang gyud sa sarili. Dili magpadala sa maling akala para dili ka madala diri sa loob, and always pray. Kung wala ang Panginoon, wala ka sa tarong karon. Isauli gyud nga dili muapil anang mga kontrabando." <i>("What's important is to trust yourself. Do not be misled by false thoughts so you won't be influenced inside, and always pray. Without God, you would not be in the right path now. Return to the right way by not joining in contraband.")</i></p>
	Humility, Gratitude, and Change	<p>IDI-PM8 (RO3; PQ3.1): "Para saakoo be strong and permi pasalamat sa ginoo." <i>("For me, be strong and always be thankful to God.")</i></p> <p>IDI-PM7 (RO3; PQ3.1): "Basin pg sa kapait sa tanang pwede nimo pwede reklamo naa gihapon butant na daghan pwede ipa salamat sa ginoo" <i>("Even if there is so much hardship that you can complain about, there are still many things to be thankful for to God.")</i></p>

Through prayer, peer interaction, and involvement in prison programs, participants found meaningful ways to care for themselves and others. These strategies served as lifelines during their lowest moments, allowing them to not only survive, but also to reflect, adapt, and gradually rebuild their sense of identity within confinement.

DISCUSSIONS

The heart of this chapter lies in interpreting the deeply personal truths shared by Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). Their narratives reveal more than just the realities of prison life, they exposed the emotional, psychological, and spiritual weight that incarceration imposes on human dignity. This discussion unpacks those experiences not as isolated accounts, but as reflections of broader societal patterns, broken systems, and the human will to endure. Guided by *Robert Merton's Strain Theory* and *Erik Erikson's*

Psychosocial Development Theory, this chapter weaves together the voices of the PDLs, the research objectives, and prior knowledge to explore how individuals survive, adapt, and seek redemption within the walls. Each insight drawn affirms that their stories are not only valid, but they are vital in reshaping how justice, rehabilitation, and humanity intersect.

Experiences of PDLs in Relation to Their Well-Being

Loss and Longing

The participants revealed that separation from their families and the abrupt loss of freedom were among the most painful aspects of incarceration. P1 shared, “Lisod gyud kaayo kay wala ko sa akong pamilya, pirmi ko mingawon ug maghilak sa gabii,” while P4 admitted, “Ang pinakalisod mao tong pagdawat nga priso na ko, mura kog nawala tanan nakong plano.” These confessions illustrate not just loneliness but the shattering of roles and responsibilities that once gave meaning to their lives. The family, as their main source of identity and support, suddenly becomes unreachable, creating a void that intensifies emotional suffering. This resonates with Erikson’s stage of intimacy versus isolation, where confinement hinders meaningful connections and leaves individuals vulnerable to despair. Similarly, Merton’s strain theory frames this longing as the result of blocked opportunities: the inability to fulfill family duties and personal aspirations produces emotional strain. Folk et al. (2019) demonstrated that incarcerated individuals who maintained frequent contact with family, through visits, calls, or letters, experienced stronger family connectedness, which in turn predicted better mental health during the first-year post-release. Similarly, Cochran (2013) found that prisoners who received consistent family visits, especially early in their sentence, had significantly lower rates of recidivism, suggesting the emotional solace of visitation reduces ongoing strain. These findings support the accounts of PDLs in this study, whose longing for family ties was centered to their emotional struggles. Thus, the theme of loss and longing emphasizes that incarceration punishes not only the individual but also the family unit, underlining the importance of family-centered prison programs.

Prison Culture and Environment

Despite these struggles, participants also shared how they adjusted to prison life by learning its norms and rules. P2 explained, “Kung unsay rules diri, sundon lang kay mao ra man pud na ang paagi para malikay sa gubot,” while P6 reflected, “Naanad ra ko kay makita man nako unsay ginabuhay sa uban, mao pud akong gisunod para makasurvive.” These statements reflect the necessity of adaptation and conformity to survive inside. Rather than existing in a vacuum, prisons form their own cultures, with codes of conduct, hierarchies, and informal systems of order. This observation reflects Goffman’s (1961) concept of “total institutions,” where individuals are resocialized under rigid systems that strip previous identities while imposing new norms. It also aligns with Erikson’s theory of identity development, as PDLs adapt to maintain a sense of belonging in an unfamiliar and restrictive environment. From Merton’s perspective, this adaptation is a response to strain: when legitimate opportunities are blocked, individuals innovate or conform within alternative systems such as prison culture. Crawley (2008) stated that prisoners develop alternative social systems as coping mechanisms, which can provide both protection and risk. Similarly, McKendy (2021) emphasized that prison culture shapes behavior and identity, often becoming a survival strategy in response to the pains of incarceration. Contextualizing these insights, the accounts of P2 and P6 show that adaptation is not merely passive obedience but an active strategy for survival. This underscores the importance of fostering constructive prison environments through structured programs that replace harmful informal systems with positive social norms.

Inner Transformation

The participants also revealed that incarceration, while painful, opened opportunities for reflection and transformation. P3 shared, “Nakadisiplina ko diri, nasugdan nako ang pag-ampo ug pagbasa sa Bibliya, mura kog nakakaplag ug bag-ong kaugalingon,” while P7 explained, “Bisan lisod, ako gihimo ang adlaw-

adlaw nga schedule para naa koy kapuslanan.” These insights highlight how discipline, faith, and structured routines allowed them to reclaim agency in an otherwise restrictive environment. These accounts demonstrate that prisoners are not entirely powerless, but instead, they actively reconstruct meaning and identity through spiritual practice and self-discipline. This reflects Erikson’s framework of psychosocial development, where crisis can serve as catalysts for renewing identity and growth. It also illustrates Merton’s concept of innovation, as participants created alternative coping mechanisms when conventional life pathways were blocked. Auty, Hulley, and Liebling (2016) states that purposeful prison activities, such as structured routines, education, or spiritual practices, significantly improved prisoners’ resilience, and their psychological well-being. Their study supports the experiences of P3 and P7, showing that engagement in meaningful practices transforms incarceration from a purely punitive state into one that fosters inner growth. Therefore, the theme of inner transformation reframes prison not only as a place of punishment but also as a potential environment for rehabilitation, provided institutions encourage such growth through faith-based programs, education, and life-skills training.

Effects of Incarceration on the Overall Well-Being of PDLs

Psychological and Emotional Impact of Incarceration

The participants described incarceration as a destabilizing experience that significantly affected their mental and emotional health. P8 revealed, “Mura kog mabaliw pirmi, maguol ko, maghunahuna nga basin wala nay pulos akong kinabuhi,” while P5 confessed, “Usahay di nako kaya, maglisod kog tulog kay sig sig kog huna-huna sa kaso ug sa pamilya.” These testimonies contextualize the prison experience as not merely the deprivation of liberty but also the erosion of psychological stability. The sense of helplessness and anxiety stemmed not only from confinement but from the uncertainty of their cases and separation from social roles. Erikson’s theory explains this condition as a disruption in identity formation, where instead of progressing through healthy stages of development, individuals experiences no growth and confusion. Similarly, Merton’s strain theory illustrates that the denial of legitimate opportunities generates stress, which manifests as emotional distress. In the study of Fazel and Seewald (2012), it is stated that prisoners are at least three times more likely to suffer from major depression and psychosis compared to the general population, underscoring the mental health risks of incarceration. Likewise, Wildeman and Muller (2012), highlighted that imprisonment often produces long-term psychological harm, not only for inmates but also for their families, reinforcing the idea that incarceration destabilizes social roles and relationships. These findings parallel the accounts of P8 and P5, whose struggles reflect the psychological toll of imprisonment. Thus, the theme of psychological and emotional impact highlights that incarceration extends beyond punishment; it undermines the mental well-being of PDLs and calls for integrated mental health services inside prisons.

Changes in Behavior and Perspective

Despite its hardships, incarceration also became a period of reflection and change for some PDLs. P4 reflected, “Daghan kog nahibal-an sa sayop nga gibuhay nako, gusto na gyud ko mausab,” while P6 shared, “Sa prisohan, nakat-on ko ug pasensya ug pag-ampo, nakabalo ko nga naa pay chance nga mausab.” These accounts reveal that imprisonment, while traumatic, can serve as a turning point where individuals reassess their past and commit to personal growth. Contextually, this suggests that incarceration is paradoxical: it produces both harm and the possibility of transformation. From Erikson’s perspective, these confessions represent a shift from role confusion toward renewed identity, where personal change is anchored in discipline and spiritual awareness. Merton’s strain theory also applies, as participants redirected strain into constructive innovation, transforming frustration into moral reckoning. Clear (2010) emphasized that faith-based and rehabilitative programs in prisons often foster spiritual awakening, giving inmates a framework to reinterpret their experiences in positive ways.

Maruna (2001) showed that when someone decides to stop doing crime is often rooted in a process of narrative transformation, where individuals change the way they look at it or think about their past

failures and embrace a reformed identity. These findings support the experiences of P4 and P6, who described incarceration not only as a punishment but also as a chance for change.

Thus, this theme underscores the importance of structured rehabilitation programs that encourage reflection and provide opportunities for spiritual and behavioral growth, ensuring that the transformative potential of imprisonment leads to genuine reformation.

Stigma and Fear of Reintegration

Beyond prison walls, participants also shared their anxiety about reintegration into society. P7 explained, “Bisan gusto nako mausab, mahadlok ko kay basin dili gihapon ko dawaton sa komunidad,” while P2 admitted, “Mao na akong kabalaka, nga bisan makagawas ko, priso ra gihapon sa panan-aw sa uban.” These statements contextualize reintegration as a continuation of punishment, where stigma and rejection create barriers to social acceptance. The fear of being permanently labeled as a criminal undermines self-esteem and hinders rehabilitation. This reflects Merton’s strain theory: even after incarceration, structural barriers prevent individuals from accessing legitimate means of rebuilding their lives. From Erikson’s view, stigma obstructs the stage of generativity, where individuals aim to contribute meaningfully to their families and communities.

Pager (2003) demonstrated through field experiments that a criminal record dramatically reduces employment opportunities, regardless of qualifications, reinforcing the stigma that participants described. Similarly, Visher and Travis (2011) found that ex-prisoners often face rejection from both potential employers and their communities, with stigma acting as a major factor in recidivism. These studies support the fears expressed by P7 and P2, showing that the challenges of reintegration are not just personal but systemic. Thus, the theme of stigma and fear of reintegration highlights a critical gap in correctional systems: the lack of post-release support and community reintegration programs. Without addressing stigma and providing structured reintegration pathways, incarceration risks becoming a cycle of punishment rather than a step toward rehabilitation.

Insights Shared by PDLs in Managing Self to Achieve Well-Being

Spiritual Resilience as Foundation of Strength

One of the most compelling insights from participants was the reliance on faith as their primary source of strength. P1 shared, “Kung wala ang Ginoo, basin nawad-an nako ug paglaum,” while P3 affirmed, “Bisan lisod, basta makapangamuyo ko, makahatag ug kalinaw sa akong huna-huna.” These statements reveal that prayer and spirituality provide emotional stability in the face of uncertainty. Contextually, faith serves as a coping mechanism that restores hope, alleviates stress, and allows PDLs to interpret suffering as meaningful. In Erikson’s psychosocial framework, this represents the cultivation of hope and integrity even in constrained circumstances. From Merton’s perspective, spirituality becomes an alternative pathway when conventional means of achieving security and peace are blocked.

Clear and Sumter (2002) found that religious involvement among inmates was strongly linked to reduced misconduct and greater psychological well-being, suggesting that spirituality provides structure and self-control. Similarly, Kerley et al. (2005) demonstrated that prisoners who engaged in prayer and religious activities reported higher levels of resilience and lower levels of stress, supporting the idea that faith mitigates the pains of incarceration. These findings mirror the experiences of P1 and P3, whose reliance on faith gave them a sense of calm and hope in prison. Thus, spirituality emerges not only as a personal coping mechanism but also as a foundation for prison-based rehabilitation programs that integrate faith and counseling, emphasizing the role of religion as a protective factor during incarceration.

Motivation Rooted in Family and Redemption

Family ties also surfaced as a dominant source of motivation for change. P5 admitted, “Ang akong pamilya maoy kusog nako, mao nang andam ko mausab para nila,” while P8 said, “Bisan priso ko, nagtan-aw ko nga makabawi ko sa akong mga anak.” These testimonies contextualize family as both a reason for

endurance and a catalyst for reformation. By anchoring their will to change on their relationships, PDLs reaffirm the importance of generativity, or the human drive to provide for and nurture others, as emphasized in Erikson's stages of development. In the framework of Merton's strain theory, when institutional pathways toward fulfilling family responsibilities are blocked, incarcerated individuals innovate by cultivating personal resolve for redemption.

Laub and Sampson (2003) demonstrated that strong family bonds are among the most significant predictors of desistance from crime, as they provide both emotional support and accountability. Similarly, Mills and Codd (2008) found that maintaining family connections during incarceration not only strengthens prisoners' resilience but also plays a vital role in successful reintegration after release. These findings mirror the experiences of P5 and P8, who drew strength from their families to endure imprisonment and envision a reformed future. Therefore, this theme emphasizes the importance of family-focused interventions in correctional settings, which preserve relationships during incarceration and strengthen motivations for rehabilitation and reintegration.

Wisdom Gained Through Hardship

The participants also demonstrated the capacity to draw moral lessons from their experiences. P6 advised, "Likayi ang bisyo kay mao nay nakadaot sa ako, magpasalamat bisan naa sa prisohan," while P7 reflected, "Kung makasala ka, dawata ang silot ug ayaw na usab." These reflections contextualize incarceration as a moral reckoning, where individuals gain humility, accountability, and gratitude despite adversity. This wisdom is not abstract but grounded in the lived pain of imprisonment, making it a valuable contribution to restorative justice approaches. Erikson's stage of integrity is reflected here, as individuals—despite stigma and suffering—find meaning in their struggles and develop a sense of moral responsibility. Merton's strain theory also applies, as the frustration of blocked opportunities is reframed into moral insights rather than destructive responses.

Maruna (2001) highlighted that many desisting offenders reinterpret their prison experiences as turning points, using lessons learned to rebuild their lives. Similarly, Giordano, Cernkovich, and Rudolph (2002) argued that "cognitive transformations," or shifts in mindset, are central to positive change, as offenders embrace new values and reject old patterns of behavior. These findings support the voices of P6 and P7, who emphasized that hardship led them toward discipline, humility, and accountability. Thus, the wisdom shared by PDLs demonstrates that prison, despite its stigma, can foster personal growth that benefits not only the individual but also the wider community—if supported through reflection opportunities and rehabilitative programs.

CONCLUSION

The insights drawn from this study revealed not only the personal experiences of PDLs but also key institutional deficiencies that affect their well-being and hinder effective rehabilitation. These gaps, voiced repeatedly through their testimonies, expose the urgent need for systemic improvement:

Inadequate Mental Health Support. Despite the prevalence of depression, anxiety, and emotional distress among PDLs, most facilities lack access to psychological counseling or therapy services.

Overcrowding and Poor Living Conditions. PDLs reported cramped cells, unsanitary conditions, and limited access to clean water and nutritious food, compromising both physical and mental health.

Delayed Legal Resolution. Several participants expressed distress over prolonged case handling and trial delays, especially for first-time offenders.

Limited Access to Rehabilitation Programs. While some programs exist, they are not available to all. Opportunities for education, livelihood, and spiritual growth are inconsistently delivered.

Lack of Post-Release Support. There are no structured reintegration systems in place to guide PDLs after their release. Social stigma persists, reducing their chances for employment and social reacceptance.

Implications

The findings across all three objectives present a rich and complex picture of life inside prison walls. The narratives reveal that incarceration is not solely about punishment but also about transformation, though this transformation is largely self-driven due to limited institutional support. The study validates Merton's and Erikson's theories in the context of Philippine correctional facilities, showing that structural inequality and developmental disruption are central to understanding the experience of PDLs. However, it also expands on these theories by highlighting how agency, spirituality, and community emerge as powerful forces for survival and growth. In sum, the voices of the PDLs emphasize the urgent need for humane, rehabilitative policies in correctional institutions. Their stories call on the justice system, particularly institutions like BJMP, to not merely detain but to heal, empower, and prepare individuals for reintegration into society. These true confessions are not merely stories of regret, but testimonies of survival, growth, and transformation. Each voice carries the weight of lived pain but also the light of personal rebirth. It is within these confessions that society can rediscover the value of second chances, and the role of compassion in justice.

Future Directions

Building on the findings and implications, the following recommendations are proposed by the researchers for key stakeholders to ensure that incarceration becomes a pathway to personal and social transformation rather than a dead-end experience.

To Jail Administrators and BJMP Officials

Institutionalize Mental Health Services. The researchers suggest that to establish a permanent mental health unit with licensed professionals, peer counselors, and therapy groups. These services should include suicide prevention protocols, especially for new inmates.

Standardize and Expand Rehabilitative Programs. The researchers suggest to ensure all PDLs have access to education, skills training, and values formation, regardless of sentence length, case type, or gender identity. They also suggest implementing progress tracking systems to monitor each inmate's growth and readiness for reintegration.

Implement Gender-Responsive Policies. The researchers suggest to acknowledge the unique needs of women and LGBTQ+ PDLs. They should provide separate but equal access to healthcare, privacy, and program participation, aligned with international standards for correctional management.

Improve Physical Conditions. The researchers suggest to address the issues of overcrowding, poor hygiene, and insufficient nutrition. Basic physiological needs must be met to support psychological and social development.

To Policymakers and Government Agencies

Review Legal Delays and Case Backlogs. The researchers suggest to expedite the legal processes, especially for minor offenses or those under pre-trial detention. The psychological burden of long, unresolved cases must be minimized.

Institutionalize Restorative Justice Frameworks. The researchers suggest to promote alternatives to incarceration for non-violent offenses through community service, probation, or reconciliation programs. This approach is cost-effective and humane.

Increase Budget for Correctional Human Development Programs. The researchers suggest to allocate a dedicated fund for rehabilitation, reintegration, and capacity-building initiatives within jails and penal institutions.

Support Post-Release Programs. The researchers suggest to establish a transitional programs and halfway houses that provide housing, employment assistance, and emotional support for former inmates during their reintegration phase.

To Civil Society Organizations and NGOs

Forge Partnerships with Correctional Facilities. The researchers suggest to extend support through volunteer teaching, skills training, therapy, and spiritual counseling. NGOs can play a key role in filling resource gaps and offering community-based reintegration paths.

Launch Public Awareness Campaigns. The researchers suggest to educate the public about the human side of incarceration to reduce stigma and discrimination. They should encourage employers and communities to give second chances.

Advocate for the Rights of the Incarcerated. The researchers suggest to monitor jail conditions, safeguarding PDL rights, and intervening in cases of abuse, neglect, or inequality.

To Future Researchers and the Academic Community

Conduct Comparative Studies. The researchers suggest that future research may compare experiences across gender, age, or region to highlight more nuanced rehabilitation needs and best practices.

Trace Post-Release Outcomes. The researchers suggest that longitudinal studies may be conducted on former PDLs to determine the sustainability of behavioral change and reintegration success.

Explore Correctional Staff Perspectives. The researchers suggest that understanding the mindset and challenges of jail personnel may offer a more holistic view of prison dynamics and how both inmates and staff can be supported.

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